

Introducing a Project-Based Learning Approach in a Course on Design of Machine Elements: a Case Study in Two Public Universities in Portugal

Diogo Neto¹, Paulo Flores²

¹ CEMMPRE, ARISE, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Coimbra, Portugal

² CEMMS-UMinho, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: diogo.neto@dem.uc.pt, pflores@dem.uminho.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824683>

Abstract

This study explores the integration of the Race Party challenge, as a project-based learning approach, in the design of machine elements courses at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho. The Race Party challenge is a pedagogical activity, in which the students, organized in teams, are required to design, develop and construct a minicar to run five meters in a flat surface, as fast as possible. Besides the instructive approach associated with traditional design of machine elements course, the students also embrace the managerial dimension of the project organization. Assignments, deliverables, laboratory activities, written reports, oral presentations and the competition at the end of the semester provide students a good number of hands-on learning experience incorporating various didactic aspects in a structured manner. Within the scope and objectives of the Race Party project, students can not only apply knowledge from previous curricular units, but also acquire and develop soft skills, such as teamwork competences. The Race Party project demands students to creatively solve open-ended problems with a clear success metric and guided sequence. The Race Party is a simple, safety and practical activity, yet it is a highly demanding project, since involves different aspects associated with the design of machines elements. Thus, the main objective of this work is to present a pilot study carried out at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho, where the Race Party challenge was implemented in a course on machine design. For this purpose, the students' voice is the key instrument utilized to assess the effectiveness of this innovative pedagogical approach. By and large, it was recognized, by students and instructors from both universities involved, that the Race Party project is successful and effective for teaching and learning machine elements design.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Race Party Challenge; Engineering Education; Design of Machine Elements.

1 Introduction

Engineering education in the 21st century is undergoing a permanent and significant transformation to meet the evolving demands of industry and society. Engineers today face increasingly complex and interdisciplinary challenges, requiring a skill set that extends beyond traditional technical knowledge (Van den Beemt et al., 2020). According to the report "Engineer of 2020" by the National Academy of Engineering (Engineering, 2004), engineers must not only be sources of technical knowledge but also possess interdisciplinary problem-solving skills to integrate concepts from various scientific and technological fields. Therefore, in addition to technical expertise, engineers need soft skills, such as communication, leadership and teamwork. Thus, an innovative approach of engineering education is required to develop this interdisciplinary knowledge and skills (Litzinger et al., 2011). This is also the American Society of Mechanical Engineers 2030 vision (Kirkpatrick et al., 2011).

Since the quality of learning is largely dependent on teaching effectiveness, traditional lecture-based instruction, particularly in engineering, is no longer suitable to provide all the professional skills needed by contemporary graduates (Cheng et al., 2013). In response to this demand, universities across the world are under increasing pressure to update the engineering curricula, aiming to address the skills gap identified above (Mitchell et al., 2021). The need for a curriculum encompassing areas such as engineering's role within society and a whole set of transversal skills from critical thinking to team working have been strongly highlighted.

Moreover, adopting teaching and learning methodologies that activates student curiosity and hands-on work should improve motivation and reduce dropout rates (Terrón-López et al., 2017). Typically, these methodologies primarily resort to pedagogical strategies associated with active learning and project-oriented approaches (Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019).

The shift from traditional lecture-based teaching to a student-centred-learning approach helps students to develop their professional skills and improve the adaptability required in the modern engineering workplaces. Adopting active learning approaches in engineering education allows students to engage directly in the learning experience, which improves the quality of learning in the short-term (Maceiras et al., 2025). Thus, active learning techniques such as project-based learning (PBL) (Gomez-del Rio & Rodriguez, 2022), flipped classrooms (Cho et al., 2021), collaborative group work, and hands-on laboratories (Gillet et al., 2005) are becoming increasingly prevalent in engineering education. These approaches not only enhance technical understanding but also foster the development of crucial transversal skills like teamwork, communication and problem-solving (McCrum, 2017).

The main objective of this work is to describe and discuss the implementation of a pedagogical project to promote the teaching-learning process of design and selection of machine elements among undergraduate students at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho. For this purpose, the Race Party Challenge was elected as a practical project, in which students, organised in teams, must design a minicar to race five meters on a horizontal and regular surface, as fast as possible. In order to make the design project more attractive and exciting for both students and instructors, the process of manufacturing and assembling of a physical prototype is also required. Within the scope and objectives of this pedagogical activity, the students will be able to develop technical skills in various areas, such as digital prototyping, mechanics, machine design, strength of materials, as well as manufacturing and assembling processes. In addition to these technical aspects, students can also develop soft skills such as teamwork, leadership and initiative, and the ability to communicate to a wide audience. The implementation of this design project embraces different pedagogical dimensions, such as lectures, laboratory activities, deliverables, written reports, oral presentations and written exams. This study discusses the impact of the proposed project-based learning approach as an effective manner to teaching machine elements in a non-traditional fashion.

The paper is organized in five main sections. Thus, after a brief introduction, Section 2 describes the Race Party competition, which is a project-based learning approach successfully applied at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho in the framework of the course Design of Machine Elements. Then, Section 3 presents the basic aspects related to the learning outcomes and assessment approaches in the spirit of the Race Party activity. In Section 4, some preliminary outcomes are presented and discussed, which allow to show a general picture of the implementation of the Race Party project at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho. Finally, in Section 5, the main concluding remarks are examined, and some potential future developments are discussed.

2 Race Party Pedagogical Activity

This section briefly describes the main features of the Race Party challenge, which was developed within the framework of a project-based learning approach. This specific pedagogical project aims to make the traditional machine design courses more applied and engaging for both students and instructors. As part of the Race Party challenge, students must develop a minicar that can travel five metres on a flat surface in the shortest possible time. For this purpose, each student team is provided with a basic kit at the beginning of the semester, which includes a piece of wood, a metal shaft, a plastic piece to support the shaft, two shaft holders and a

helical spring. Figure 1a shows the basic kit provided to the students, which must be considered during the design and construction of the minicar.

The main objective of the Race Party challenge is to design and build a dragster-type minicar, powered by a tensioned helical spring. Figure 1b shows an example of the minicar designed by a student team. The performance and success of the race will be judged on aesthetics, speed and reliability. The racetrack is shown in Figure 1c, with the start and finish lines separated by five meters. The educational activity of the Race Party includes lectures in traditional classroom presentations to discuss specific topics, such as dimensional metrology, safety rules in laboratories, dynamics of mechanical systems, design of machine elements, materials and selection of mechanical components, just to name a few. Students are expected to come prepared for lectures by reviewing the relevant course materials, including slides, textbooks, and YouTube videos. It should be noted that students spend a considerable amount of time developing and designing their solutions, as well as familiarizing themselves with the laboratories and machine shop.

Figure 1. Race Party challenge: (a) basic kit provided to each student team; (b) example of a minicar developed; (c) racetrack used for the competition.

In the Race Party pedagogical activity, there are some key tasks and milestones to be carried out by the students, namely: (i) evaluate the spring stiffness using both analytical and experimental approaches; (ii) design and conceptualise the minicar solution, including the number of wheels, body aesthetics, and other factors; (iii) evaluate the dynamic performance of the minicar using a specific computational code developed for this purpose; (iv) develop a CAD/CAE/CAM model of the final minicar design for structural analysis and manufacturing; (v) select materials and mechanical components to build the physical prototype of the optimized solution for preliminary testing; (vi) exhibit the final version of the minicar during the Race Party competition.

Other important characteristics of the minicar developed as part of the Race Party project are: originality, simplicity, safety, portability, cost and adaptability to different conditions. However, all options and decisions made during this design project must be supported by engineering and scientific principles of mechanics. At the end of each task, each student team must submit a one-page report summarizing the key aspects and conclusions reached. In addition, each student team must give five oral presentations detailing the work carried out and the results obtained. The main purpose of using these tools is to encourage discussion with students about the process and product of the Race Party challenge. In particular, potential difficulties and conflicts within the teams can be identified and addressed in a timely manner.

Additionally, after the race, each team must create a short video summarizing the key aspects of the Race Party challenge. Students are informed of this requirement at the beginning of the semester and are encouraged to take photos and collect videos of all tasks and activities throughout the semester. Students are also required

to maintain and update their portfolio, which is regularly reviewed by both the tutor and the course coordinator. The main goal of using the portfolio approach is to actively engage students in the learning process related to the Race Party project, allowing them to track the progress of their individual and team contributions throughout the semester.

The activities and progress of the teams, as well as of each individual student, will be monitored through their attendance at the scheduled sessions. To facilitate this process, each student team is required to present their portfolio. Moreover, students are required to give mid-term and final oral presentations, produce mid-term and final reports, complete a series of deliverables and take three individual mini-exams. This wide range of aspects not only allows for continuous monitoring of the project's progress, but also facilitates the assessment and grading of both teams and individual students. It also exposes students to different learning techniques, which ultimately prove effective in achieving better results.

Success in this design project depends on teamwork. Students will be assigned to teams of five who will work together throughout the semester. It is expected that students within a team will work together on the design project, homework and other educational activities within the class. It is of paramount importance that teams deal with this in a positive and constructive manner. Teams that have problems working together should make every effort to resolve them themselves. Course instructors are always available to help and facilitate the smooth running of the team, but the ultimate responsibility lies with the team.

3 Learning Objectives and Assessment

The central idea of the Race Party challenge is to provide each student with a deep understanding of the dynamics and design of machine elements. Students will also acquire and develop technical skills in the selection of materials and mechanical components, mechanism design and manufacturing processes. In addition to these hard skills, students are also expected to acquire and develop soft skills such as teamwork, creativity, the ability to communicate with a wide audience and the ability to defend their views. In addition to the learning outcomes related to the Machine Elements courses, in which the Race Party challenge is included, there are specific learning outcomes directly related to this pedagogical project. Thus, at the end of the course, the students must be able to achieve, either individually or in team, at least the following objectives (i) identify the key variables related to the dynamics and performance of minicars; (ii) carry out basic kinematic and dynamic analysis of mechanical systems; (iii) design a machine for a specific purpose (performance, functionality, manufacturability); (iv) develop computational and physical models of machines and mechanisms for simulation, design and optimisation; (v) produce CAD models and technical drawings suitable for communication with the machine shop technician (vi) identify and select materials and mechanical components to build a machine; (vii) build, assemble and test a mechanical system using standard components.

Despite its simplicity, the Race Party project is a demanding pedagogical activity, encompassing multiple aspects related to mechanical system dynamics, design and selection of machine elements, as well as numerous assessment requirements. Notably, this project strongly adopts the assessment for learning approach, which not only motivates students but also enhances their learning process. Therefore, the assessment and grading of students in this project are based on the following components: (i) deliverables (maximum 1 page per submission); (ii) mini-exams (15 minutes each); (iii) final exam (30 minutes); (iv) mid-term oral presentation (30 minutes, including discussion); (v) final oral presentation (30 minutes, including discussion); (vi) mid-term report (maximum of 6 pages, excluding appendices); (vii) final report (maximum of 12 pages, excluding appendices). The weighting of each component may vary from year to year, based on the lecturers' experience and student feedback, which is collected and discussed during the first lecture of the semester.

Overall, the Race Party project is assessed on the merit of the students, which includes both the progress and the final product, as well as the quality of their reports and presentations. Furthermore, peer and self-assessment are encouraged throughout the semester, providing students with valuable feedback on their skills and comfort level in carrying out the various tasks associated with the project. In this pedagogical project, students are organized in teams, and each team is supervised by a tutor, who is faculty member. By organizing students into teams, they can acquire and develop teamwork skills. It should be emphasized that the tutors provide students with any clarifications and explanations needed throughout the semester, but they are not directly involved in the decisions made by the students. The activities and progress of the groups, as well as each individual student, are monitored through their attendance at the scheduled sessions.

During the semester, there are specific weeks, where students, in team, can reflect on the following questions: (i) "Within the Race Party project we have learned ..."; (ii) "We have difficulties in ..."; (iii) "We need help and support in ..."; (iv) "The team works well in ..."; (v) "The team can improve in ...". It should be noticed that, apparently simple, these questions reveal to be quite demanding and hard to be answered by students, since they are used to answering technical and direct questions. This has been an ongoing challenge for instructors in adjusting and improving the Race Party project over the years. In fact, this has been a tremendous challenge for instructors in terms of adjust and improve the Race Party project over the years. In addition, students are also asked to respond to a set of open questions such as: (i) "For me the most interesting aspects were ... because ...", (ii) "If I could give advice to future students of this course, I would tell them that ..."; (iii) "If I started this course today ...", (iv) "If I could give advice to future students of this course, I would tell them that ...".

4 Results and Discussion

This section deals with some preliminary findings that resulting from the implementation of the Race Party project at the University of Coimbra and the University of Minho, specifically within the Machine Elements course. Incorporating the Race Party activity into the syllabus was a demanding task, requiring substantial adjustments in the preparation and reorganization of the course. Originally, the course was structured around practical problems and exercises, following a learning-by-doing approach. The transition to a project-based learning methodology required careful planning and simplification of certain course elements in order to effectively integrate hands-on activities, while maintaining the core learning objectives. One of the key aspects was the establishment of milestones associated with the development of the project, allowing for student self-regulation as well as providing appropriate and timely feedback to the teams.

The Race Party project has demonstrated significant benefits to engineering education, particularly in improving students' understanding of dynamics of systems and design of machine elements. Throughout the course, students have successfully applied the theoretical knowledge to create an engineering solution (minicar) capable of fulfilling the required specifications, thereby strengthening their problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. The integration of computational and physical modelling has enabled students to refine their designs and optimise performance. Indeed, digital prototyping using CAD software and simulation techniques replaced the traditional trial-and-error approach, allowing students to quickly anticipate potential design problems, virtually test different configurations and resolve issues before building the physical prototype. This approach improved efficiency, reduced development time, and minimized costly errors.

The gradual improvement in students' ability to communicate effectively, both orally and in writing, is one of the key observations from this pedagogical project, as occurred in previous studies graduates (Cheng et al., 2013). The incremental assessment process, including reports and oral presentations, has significantly reinforced the importance of clear and structured communication in engineering. Moreover, the feedback from reports and presentations allows students to critically evaluate their own work and justify their decisions based

on technical evidence. This process promotes a deeper understanding of the subject as students are required not only to solve the engineering problem, but also to communicate their solutions to an audience that may not have the same technical background. In addition, students have developed visual communication skills, particularly through the use of CAD models and simulation results. These visual aids are powerful tools for explaining complex ideas, making their concepts more accessible and persuasive to a diverse audience.

The Race Party placed a strong emphasis on teamwork, recognizing that successful engineering outcomes are often the result of effective collaboration rather than individual effort. The need to coordinate and collaborate with team members helped students to develop key interpersonal skills such as active listening, negotiation and compromise. These skills are essential in engineering practice, where complex projects often require collaboration across different disciplines and expertise. Students learned how to manage differing opinions and ensure that all team members contributed their knowledge and ideas. Students were exposed to the importance of delegation and sharing responsibility. Effective teamwork involves understanding the strengths and weaknesses of each team member and assigning tasks accordingly. Through this project, students gained insight into how to optimise team performance by using the skills and talents of each team member.

The implementation of the Race Party within the Machine Elements course at both universities resulted in improved student academic performance, compared to traditional assessment methods based solely on a final exam. It was found that the final grade average was higher and the success rate was better compared to previous editions of the course without the Race Party project. Moreover, this engineering education project also contributed to a significant reduction in the number of students failing the course. Rather than focusing solely on a single high-stakes exam, students took a range of assessments, including reports, presentations and mini-exams, which encouraged regular study and active participation. As a result, students were better prepared and more confident in applying their knowledge, leading to improved performance and a more comprehensive understanding of the subject. The improved student's performance was also reported by (Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019). The continuous nature of the learning process, combined with the practical application of concepts, proved to be more effective than relying on a final exam alone.

Student feedback, collected through anonymous surveys carried out at the end of semester, further reinforces the effectiveness of the Race Party project. Most students reported feeling more engaged and motivated compared to traditional lecture-based courses, which agrees with previous studies (Maceiras et al., 2025; Terrón-López et al., 2017). Another relevant outcome, which can be verified at both universities, relates to class attendance during the semester. Figure 2 shows students' perceptions of class attendance during the semester, comparing the two universities. As far as the University of Coimbra is concerned (Figure 2a), the percentage of students who attended at least 80% of classes increased from 45% to 58% after the application of the Race Party project. On the other hand, the percentage of students who attended less than 20% of classes decreased from 12% to 5%. The same result was obtained at the University of Minho (Figure 2b), where the percentage of students who attended 100% of classes increased, while the percentage of students who attended less than 50% of classes decreased. The survey results confirm that increased student attendance, together with their participation in the Race Party, was a key factor in the academic success of the Machine Elements course.

Figure 2. Perception of the students in relation to the attendance of classes during the semester: (a) University of Coimbra; (b) University of Minho

Student testimonials further highlight the positive impact of the Race Party on their learning experience:

- *"Excellent initiative by Professor [name omitted] for the car race initiative. I think that assembling and developing these cars made me realize and understand some of the concepts better in a more challenging and fun way"*, [anonymous response from a student, University of Coimbra]
- *"The idea of including a car race (Race Party) as a practical part was simply brilliant, this approach made learning much more dynamic and interesting"*, [anonymous response from a student, University of Coimbra]
- *"I believe that this evaluation system is really important for future students and that despite it also being challenging for the teacher, I think that it is a job that the students will always remember as a unique and fun job"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Coimbra]
- *"Overall, I was very satisfied with the learning I obtained in this subject and I would like to highlight the merit of the teacher [name omitted], for his initiative with the "Race Party" project and for the way he helped and motivated his students"*, [anonymous response from a student, University of Coimbra]
- *"Creating a project like "Race Party" encouraged students to want to learn even more and made the course even more interesting. The objective and clear way of teaching classes, both theoretical and practical, helped them understand the subject in the best possible way"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Coimbra]
- *"The Curricular Unit was the best I have ever had. Professor [name omitted] is the type of professor that I wish existed in all UCs. His interest in student learning, knowledge and concern for his UC was impeccable"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Minho]
- *"In general, the course is very interesting and rewarding, as it demonstrates the results of the effort made throughout the semester in a more perceptible way, at a practical level"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Minho]
- *"Personally, it was one of the courses that most interested me so far. This is due to its strong practical aspect, which has proven to be something rare"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Minho]
- *"Professor [name omitted] was able to motivate students in relation to the projects to be developed and showed that he was always available to clarify possible doubts"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Minho]
- *"More subjects like this"* [anonymous response from a student, University of Minho].

Finally, it is worth mentioning that, while the Race Party challenge left instructors thoroughly exhausted by the end of the semester, they also felt deeply fulfilled and motivated by the students' enthusiasm and success. Figure 3 shows photos of the group of students from the University of Coimbra and the University of Minho. In fact, the Race Party project transformed the learning environment, shifting the focus from a teacher-centred approach to a student-driven experience. This transformation requires flexibility from instructors to accommodate students' difficulties and adapt the subjects covered throughout the semester, ensuring a more personalized and effective learning experience.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Family pictures of students and instructors: (a) University of Coimbra; (b) University of Minho

5 Conclusions

The Race Party competition, a project-based learning approach, was implemented in the existing Machine Elements course at the Universities of Coimbra and Minho. The syllabus was adjusted to accommodate the Race Party project, in terms of teaching approach, learning objectives and assessment. By integrating hands-on design, prototyping, and competition, this pedagogical activity bridged the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, promoting deeper understanding and engagement among students. The project not only strengthened technical skills in machine design, dynamics and materials selection but also developed essential soft skills such as teamwork, communication and problem-solving. Key outcomes from the Race Party challenge included better academic performance, higher class attendance and reduced dropout rates, evidenced by student feedback and institutional data. The incremental assessment framework, combining reports, presentations and mini-exams, were more effective than traditional exam-based evaluation. Students praised the initiative, highlighting it as a standout experience in their education. For instructors, the Race Party was both demanding and rewarding, requiring adaptability to student needs while shifting the classroom dynamic toward student-centred learning. Despite the challenges, the success of the project highlights the value of active learning methods in preparing engineers for interdisciplinary, real-world challenges. Future iterations could explore scaling this educational model to other engineering subjects. The

Race Party is an example of how innovative PBL approaches can transform engineering education, align with industry needs and inspire the next generation of engineers.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by FCT – *Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia* within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00285: Centre for Mechanical Engineering, Materials and Processes and UID/04436: *Centro de Microssistemas Eletromecânicos da Universidade do Minho* (CMEMS-UMinho). The authors would like to acknowledge all the students that participated in the Race Party pedagogical experience both in the University of Coimbra and University of Minho.

References

- Cheng, W., Wu, X., Zhang, Z., Liu, F., Zhang, M., & Guo, P. (2013). Effective Project-Oriented Approach for Training Professional Mechanical Engineers in Undergraduate Education. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering Education*, 41(4), 289–296. <https://doi.org/10.7227/IJME.41.4.3>
- Cho, H. J., Zhao, K., Lee, C. R., Runshe, D., & Krousgrill, C. (2021). Active learning through flipped classroom in mechanical engineering: improving students' perception of learning and performance. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 8(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40594-021-00302-2>
- Engineering, N. A. of. (2004). *The Engineer of 2020: Visions of Engineering in the New Century*. The Engineer of 2020. <https://doi.org/10.17226/10999>
- Gillet, D., Nguyen Ngoc, A. V., & Reik, Y. (2005). Collaborative web-based experimentation in flexible engineering education. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 48(4), 696–704. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2005.852592>
- Gomez-del Rio, T., & Rodriguez, J. (2022). Design and assessment of a project-based learning in a laboratory for integrating knowledge and improving engineering design skills. *Education for Chemical Engineers*, 40, 17–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECE.2022.04.002>
- Hernández-de-Menéndez, M., Vallejo Guevara, A., Tudón Martínez, J. C., Hernández Alcántara, D., & Morales-Menendez, R. (2019). Active learning in engineering education. A review of fundamentals, best practices and experiences. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing*, 13(3), 909–922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12008-019-00557-8>
- Kirkpatrick, A. T., Danielson, S., Warrington, R. O., Smith, R. N., Thole, K. A., Wepfer, W. J., & Perry, T. (2011). Vision 2030 - Creating the future of mechanical engineering education. *ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition*, 22–1667.
- Litzinger, T. A., Lattuca, L. R., Hadgraft, R. G., Newstetter, W. C., Alley, M., Atman, C., DiBiasio, D., Finelli, C., Diefes-Dux, H., Kolmos, A., Riley, D., Sheppard, S., Weimer, M., & Yasuhara, K. (2011). Engineering Education and the Development of Expertise. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 100(1), 123–150. <https://doi.org/10.1002/J.2168-9830.2011.TB00006.X>
- Maceiras, R., Feijoo, J., Alfonsin, V., & Perez-Rial, L. (2025). Effectiveness of active learning techniques in knowledge retention among engineering students. *Education for Chemical Engineers*, 51, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECE.2025.01.003>
- McCrum, D. P. (2017). Evaluation of creative problem-solving abilities in undergraduate structural engineers through interdisciplinary problem-based learning. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(6), 684–700. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2016.1216089>
- Mitchell, J. E., Nyamapfene, A., Roach, K., & Tilley, E. (2021). Faculty wide curriculum reform: the integrated engineering programme. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 46(1), 48–66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2019.1593324>
- Terrón-López, M. J., García-García, M. J., Velasco-Quintana, P. J., Ocampo, J., Vigil Montaña, M. R., & Gaya-López, M. C. (2017). Implementation of a project-based engineering school: increasing student motivation and relevant learning. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(6), 618–631. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2016.1209462>
- Van den Beemt, A., MacLeod, M., Van der Veen, J., Van de Ven, A., van Baalen, S., Klaassen, R., & Boon, M. (2020). Interdisciplinary engineering education: A review of vision, teaching, and support. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 109(3), 508–555. <https://doi.org/10.1002/JEE.20347>